

Verification and Scaling of Time-Dependent Shift Using the AZURV1 Benchmark

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INTRODUCTION

Shift [1] is a massively-parallel Monte Carlo radiation transport code developed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory. In its current official release, Shift can perform k-eigenvalue and fixed source solves on CPUs and GPUs, and has demonstrated high performance on up to 1000 nodes of the Summit supercomputer [2].

The Center for Exascale Monte Carlo Neutron Transport (CEMeNT), which aims to create dynamic neutron transport simulation capabilities for use on high-performance computing architectures, has modified Shift to perform time-dependent neutron transport. In brief, this has been accomplished by placing an outer time-stepping loop over the existing transport algorithm in Shift and persistently tracking the age of particles as they move throughout the problem domain.

The remainder of this paper details verification of CEMeNT's time-dependent variant of Shift using the AZURV1 benchmark [3]. Scaling analyses investigating the performance impact of tally communication are also presented.

AZURV1 BENCHMARK

The AZURV1 benchmark, by Ganapol et al., consists of a one-dimensional, time-dependent problem in an infinite homogeneous medium with a single energy group. Scattering is treated as isotropic, and the only source is an initial external source. In plane geometry, Ganapol et al. present the governing transport equation, with boundary and initial conditions, as

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + 1 \right] \psi(x, \mu, t) = \frac{c}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \psi(x, \mu', t) d\mu' + \frac{1}{2} \delta(x) \delta(t), \quad (1a)$$

$$\lim_{|x| \rightarrow \infty} \psi(x, \mu, t) = 0, \quad \psi(x, \mu, 0) = 0. \quad (1b)$$

We note that to arrive at Eq. (1a) from a more general form of the time-dependent neutron transport equation, the neutron velocity v and the total cross section Σ_t can be assumed to be 1.0 cm s^{-1} and 1.0 cm^{-1} , respectively. Under this interpretation, c can be viewed as the isotropic scattering cross section Σ_s .

The analytical scalar flux,

$$\phi(x, t) = \int_{-1}^1 \psi(x, \mu', t) d\mu'$$

also from Ganapol et al., is shown below in Eq. 2a:

$$\phi(x, t) = \frac{e^{-t}}{2t} \left[1 + \frac{ct}{4\pi} (1 - \eta^2) \int_0^\infty \sec^2\left(\frac{\mu}{2}\right) \Re\left(\xi^2 e^{\frac{c}{2}(1-\eta^2)\xi}\right) d\mu \right] H(1 - |\eta|), \quad (2a)$$

where

$$\eta = \frac{x}{t}, \quad \xi(\mu) = \frac{\ln(q) + i\mu}{\eta + i \tan\left(\frac{\mu}{2}\right)}, \quad q = \frac{1 + \eta}{1 - \eta}, \quad (2b)$$

\Re is the real operator, and $H(z)$ is the heaviside function

$$H(z) = \begin{cases} 0, & z < 0 \\ 1, & z \geq 0 \end{cases}. \quad (2c)$$

(We note that in Reference [3], the heaviside function that appears in Eq. (2a) is absent, and was most likely omitted by mistake.)

As evidenced by Eq. (2), the AZURV1 benchmark is time- and space-dependent, offering a more comprehensive verification than simpler problems such as an infinite purely absorbing medium, which excludes scattering physics and whose solution is spatially uniform.

A visualization of Eq. (2a) is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. AZURV1 benchmark solution for $c = 0.9$ from 0-10 seconds

A pulse-like flux is observed at 1.0 s. In subsequent times, and consistent with the assumed neutron velocity, the pulse edges advance at 1.0 cm/s.

CONVERGENCE STUDIES

Shift modeling parameters

The AZURV1 benchmark was modelled using Shift's multigroup physics package. The planar geometry assumed

in Eq. (1a) was specified on a 3D Cartesian domain by defining reflective boundaries on the z- and y-axes, and defining the remaining x-axis from -20 cm to 20 cm with vacuum boundaries. An initial source of mono-energetic neutrons was defined at $x = 0$. The multigroup nuclear data for the homogeneous medium is given in Table I, in addition to the neutron energy of the initial source.

TABLE I. Total and scattering cross sections of the homogeneous medium. E is the energy of the initial neutron source, and converts to a speed of 1 cm/s.

Σ_t [cm ⁻¹]	Σ_s [cm ⁻¹]	E [eV]
1.0	0.9	5.227E-13

Simulations were conducted with the number of histories ranging from 1E3 to 1E8. Ten uniform time steps of 1.0 s were simulated, with cell-average and surface flux tallies scored on each step. Details of these tallies and comparisons to the AZURV1 benchmark solution are detailed in the following sections.

Cell-average flux

A mesh tally with 101 equal-length cells spanning $x \in [-20, 20]$ was defined in Shift. The tallied flux calculated with Shift on the final step was compared to a flux obtained from averaging Eq. (2a) over $x \in [x_{i-1/2}, x_{i+1/2}]$ and $t \in [9.0, 10.0]$,

$$\Phi_{ij} = \frac{1}{\Delta x} \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_{x_{i-1/2}}^{x_{i+1/2}} \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \phi(x', t') dx dt. \quad (3)$$

The inf- and 2-norm of the error between the exact and Shift-simulated cell-average fluxes as a function of the number of histories are shown in Figure 2. Both norms in Figure 2 exhibit the expected 1/2-order convergence rate.

Surface flux

A mesh surface tally was also defined in Shift, characterized by 102 surfaces separated by equal length. The tally domain again spanned $x \in [-20, 20]$. In this case, the tallied flux calculated with Shift on the final step was compared to the time-averaged flux obtained from averaging Eq. (2a) over $t \in [9.0, 10.0]$ at the location of cell surfaces.

$$\Phi_{i\pm 1/2, j} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \phi(x_{i\pm 1/2}, t') dx dt. \quad (4)$$

Norms of the error between the exact and Shift-simulated surface fluxes as a function of the number of particles simulated are shown in Figure 3. Once again, we observe that both norms exhibit the expected 1/2-order convergence rate.

SCALING STUDIES

CEMeNT's time-dependent implementation of Shift requires communication between all MPI ranks at the end of each time step. During this communication, the tally scores on each MPI rank are collected, and the collective mean and

Fig. 2. Convergence study for cell-average flux of AZURV1 benchmark

Fig. 3. Convergence study for surface flux of AZURV1 benchmark

variance are calculated and output to an HDF5 file. This approach avoids storing tallies on multiple time steps, which could be memory prohibitive in many practical problems. As communication is required at the end of each time step, however, performance may suffer as the number of MPI ranks increases, particularly so if the size of the tally data structure is large.

A study was conducted to examine the impact of this communication on the weak scaling efficiency of time-dependent Shift. Domain-replicated simulations of the AZURV1 benchmark were conducted with the number of MPI ranks ranging from 1 to 8000 and tallies (the cell-average and surface tallies described in the previous sections) defined with 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 , or 10^5 mesh cells. Each MPI rank was assigned 10^6 neutron histories.

In contrast to the verification simulation, 1000 uniform time steps of 1 s in length were simulated, and Σ_s was set to 0.999. The scattering cross section was changed to ensure each MPI rank had live particles to transport for the entirety of the simulation. In fact, with the noted scattering cross section, virtually all neutrons survived to the end of the simulation.

Simulations were conducted on the Lassen supercomputer at LLNL, which features 795 nodes with 44 IBM Power9 CPUs per node. Table II shows the weak scaling efficiencies of time-dependent Shift for 10^6 histories per MPI rank. Table IV details serial runtimes, which are used as reference values for the weak scaling efficiencies found in Table II.

Table II demonstrates admirable weak scaling efficiencies across for all execution configurations. We observe, generally, that the scaling efficiencies decrease as the number of MPI ranks increases, but still exceed 0.89 in all cases. The case characterized by the most costly communication ($M = 10^5$ on 8000 MPI ranks) exhibited a roughly 10% decrease in efficiency, however, 800,000% more neutron histories were

simulated relative to the serial case.

Weak scaling efficiencies were also measured for execution configurations assigning 10^4 neutron histories per MPI rank, rather than 10^6 . This change greatly decreases the amount of time each MPI rank spends actively transporting particles, while the time spent communicating is unchanged. Serial runtimes are shown in Table V. For this case, we find the efficiencies, detailed in Table III, degrade significantly as the number of MPI ranks exceeds 800. This trend is observed for all M .

TABLE IV. Serial runtimes for 10^6 neutron histories. M is the number of tally mesh cells.

M	Runtime (minutes)
10^2	92.07
10^3	110.20
10^4	117.34
10^5	165.92

TABLE V. Serial runtimes for 10^4 neutron histories. M is the number of tally mesh cells.

M	Runtime (minutes)
10^2	0.96
10^3	1.15
10^4	1.24
10^5	2.00

This suggests that to maximize the performance of time-dependent Shift using a step-wise output, the workload (i.e., the number of neutron histories) assigned to each MPI rank should be as large as permitted by memory limitations. The strong-scaling or speed-up analysis in Figure 4, where a fixed

TABLE II. Weak scaling of AZURV1 benchmark solution as a function of MPI ranks and number of mesh cells for 10^6 neutron histories per rank. M is the number of tally mesh cells.

		MPI Ranks								
		1	40	80	200	400	800	2000	4000	8000
M	10^2	1.0000	0.9500	0.9539	0.9458	0.9476	0.9190	0.9369	0.9312	0.8974
	10^3	1.0000	0.9587	0.9596	0.9498	0.9489	0.8890	0.9420	0.9381	0.9061
	10^4	1.0000	0.9574	0.9544	0.9525	0.9412	0.9254	0.9360	0.9368	0.9082
	10^5	1.0000	0.9522	0.9460	0.9532	0.9377	0.8970	0.8956	0.9269	0.8938

TABLE III. Weak scaling of AZURV1 benchmark solution as a function of MPI ranks and number of mesh cells for 10^4 neutron histories per rank. M is the number of tally mesh cells.

		MPI Ranks								
		1	40	80	200	400	800	2000	4000	8000
M	10^2	1.0000	0.9029	0.8960	0.7746	0.6567	0.5456	0.4239	0.4634	0.4593
	10^3	1.0000	0.9377	0.9142	0.8177	0.6890	0.5793	0.4579	0.4684	0.4767
	10^4	1.0000	0.9367	0.8911	0.8381	0.6978	0.6109	0.4838	0.4338	0.4869
	10^5	1.0000	0.8049	0.8136	0.8188	0.7609	0.6888	0.4988	0.4209	0.3837

Fig. 4. Speed-up in simulation of AZURV1 benchmark using 10^6 neutrons and 10^5 tally mesh cells. Neutrons were uniformly distributed amongst MPI ranks. Serial runtime was 165.92 minutes.

number of neutron histories was simulated with 1-8000 MPI ranks, further supports this suggestion. Although scaling is relatively close to ideal up to 80 MPI ranks, we observe speed-up flatten at around 800. After 2000 MPI ranks, increased parallelism produces relatively slower runtimes due to the overhead cost of communication.

We note that several of the execution configurations in Figure 4 are extreme for 10^6 histories. For example, the 8000 MPI rank case assigns 125 neutron histories per rank and spends only 2.5% of runtime transporting neutrons. Although this may not be a practical execution configuration, it serves to examine limitations of the implemented time-dependent algorithm.

CONCLUSIONS

Previous efforts to verify CEMeNT’s time-dependent features of Shift considered simple space-independent problems with purely absorbing media. The AZURV1 benchmark has allowed for a more robust verification of these features, as it involves scattering and absorption physics, and is time- and space-dependent. As the errors in the tallied cell-average and surface fluxes exhibited the expected convergence behavior as a function of particle histories, we have confidence that the time-dependent features of Shift are correctly implemented, and confirmation that these features work correctly in a space-dependent problem.

Scaling analyses were conducted to evaluate the performance impacts of the step-wise tally output approach implemented in the time-dependent mode of Shift. Results suggest that to mitigate performance loss due to the MPI communi-

cation required to finalize tally data on each time step, the number of particle histories assigned to each MPI rank should be as large as permitted by memory limitations. For domain-replicated parallelism, these limitations could be significant for large problems with detailed tallies.

CEMeNT’s time-dependent implementation of Shift is currently CPU-only. Future work will expand execution to GPUs, after which similar verification and performance analyses will be conducted. Further scaling studies investigating the influence of load imbalance are also planned.

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